

A Descriptive Study to Assess the Impact of Online Teaching on Perception of Parents among School Going Students in Education and Health During Covid-19

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ABSTRACT:

Introduction: Online teaching has widely promoted during COVID-19 pandemic to continue education among students. The study explores the Parents perception that the critical implication of e-learning in improving the nature of students “learning is making them synchronized or lined up with present day students. The aim of the study was to evaluate the parents perception of online teaching among school going students in education and health during COVID-19 pandemic.

Materials and methods: cross sectional study was carried out with 75 samples that met the inclusion criteria were selected using convenience sampling technique. Questionnaires was used to collect the data among participants which contains demographic variables, education and health regarding online teaching during COVID-19.

Result: The findings of the study reveals that there is significantly association with the level of parents perception on online teaching among school going students in education during COVID-19 at $p < 0.05$ with selected demographic variables, and there is no significant association with the level of parents perception on online teaching among school going students in health during COVID-19.

Conclusion: findings of the present study reveals that, the parents perception had a moderately favorable attitude towards online teaching among school going students. The result of this study may be utilized as a baseline for planning awareness campaigns in the future.

KEYWORDS: COVID-19, Online learning, Parents’ perception, School going students.

INTRODUCTION

COVID 19 is a respiratory infection caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome. Coronavirus 2 [SARS – CoV 2]. A novel coronavirus was identified in 2019 in Wuhan china. COVID – 19 is also known as Coronavirus disease (1). Transmission mainly occurs via direct contact or aerosol droplets. The infection may present asymptotically or with fever and dry cough, causes of this serious covid 19 include Coronavirus [CoV] are a family of enveloped, positive- sense, singlestranded RNA (+sRNA) viruses. They tend to cause mild respiratory disease in humans. These situations make the incorporate restrictions in travelling, obligatory quarantine for those who are travelled, prohibitions on get together, social distancing, curfew, ban on school and colleges, business restrictions, requesting individuals to work from home, self-isolations and lock down. In current situation Education can become transformative when teachers and students synthesize information across subjects and experiences, critically weigh significantly different perspectives, and incorporate various inquiries. A by-product of fostering critical learning spaces, in which students are encouraged to increase their capacities of analysis, imagination, critical synthesis, creative expression, self- awareness, and intentionality. It is becoming increasingly common at many higher education institutions, offering fully online blended courses in instruction with faceto- face teaching (8).

Online classes are a sort of distance learning that by and large refers to any course of study that is refined solely through the Internet (2). Schools and colleges these days are seen to be busy in online classes. (3) concluded about Parents perception that the critical implication of e-learning in improving the nature of students “learning is making them synchronized or lined up with present day

students. In detail terms, students can take part and cooperate teachers found any place across the world (7). The implementation of distance learning to ensure education continues and inhibit the spread of the Covid-19 pandemic does not mean that it does not face challenges and obstacles. In addition to positive benefits such as accelerating technology integration, information, and communication in learning activities, some obstacles are also faced. Among others, teachers and students are not used to using a fully formulated and fully online learning system.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Non experimental – descriptive study was conducted to assess the impact of online teaching on perception of parents among school going students in education and health during COVID-19 with 75 parents in chinna porur urban primary health Center through questionnaire method. the participants were selected using convenience sampling technique who met the inclusion criteria, Parents who have school going children's and attending online classes, who could understand and speak Tamil and who were willing to participate in this study. The tool used for the study was demographic variables, Likert item questionnaires to assess the parents perception towards online teaching among childrens in education and health during COVID-19. The total of 32 questions. The characteristics were described using frequency and percentage. Chi-square test is used to association of level of parents perception on impact of online teaching among school going students in education and health during COVID-19 with selected demographic variables. The collected data was analyzed by using descriptive and inferential statistics.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. To assess the demographic variable of the parents among school going children.

The current study reveals that most of the parents of school going students, 46(61.3%) were aged between 31 – 40 years, 44(58.7%) were male, 60(80%) belonged to nuclear family, 48(64%) were Hindus, 75(100%) were living in urban area, 48(64%) were studying 6th – 10th standard, 44(58.7%) were working women and had monthly income of 20,000 – 30,000 and 48(64%) had online class for 6 hrs.

The current study findings were supported by Yijun Ye, CixinWang et al (May 2021) Conducted a study on Parenting and Teacher–Student Relationship as Protective Factors for Chinese Adolescent Adjustment During COVID-19 and they concluded that among 733 middle school students (54.3% were boys) and their parents (Mage= 44.76 years, SD = 4.13 years, 28.1%fathers and 71.9% mothers) from Beijing, China.

2. To assess the perception of parents among school going student's education in online classes.

The current Study reveals that 56(74.67%) had moderately favourable attitude and 19(25.33%) had favourable attitude in education, and 62(82.67%) had moderately favourable attitude and 13(17.33%) had favourable attitude in health on impact of online teaching among school going students.

The current study findings were supported by the study conducted by Chaya heba, Salem sultan [October 29, 2020]: conducted a study on parents views of their childrens online learning in the UAE context during the COVID-19 pandemic, A concurrent mixed method design is used with the sample of 122 parents, the result shows that the parents suggestions to improve online learning were revealed, the need for more interactive live sessions between teachers and students and more communication between school and parents were the parents are most repeated suggestions for better online learning quality and experiences.

Table 1: Frequency and percentage distribution of level of perception of parents on impact of online teaching among school going students in education.

Level of Acceptance	No.	%
Unfavourable attitude ($\leq 50\%$)	0	0
Moderately Favourable attitude (51 – 75%)	56	74.67
Favourable attitude ($>75\%$)	19	25.33

Table 2: Frequency and percentage distribution of level of perception of parents on impact of online teaching among school going students in health.

Level of Acceptance	No.	%
Unfavourable attitude ($\leq 50\%$)	0	0
Moderately Favourable attitude (51 – 75%)	13	17.33
Favourable attitude ($>75\%$)	62	82.67

3. To associate the demographic variable of parents of school going students.

The current study shows that most of the parents of school going students, 46(61.3%) were aged between 31 – 40 years, 44(58.7%) were male, 60(80%) belonged to nuclear family, 48(64%) were Hindus, 75(100%) were living in urban area, 48(64%) were studying 6th – 10th standard, 44(58.7%) were working women and had monthly income of 20,000 – 30,000 and 48(64%) had online class for 6 hrs.

The current study findings were supported by the study conducted by Yijun Ye, CixinWang et al (May 2021) Conducted a study on Parenting and Teacher–Student Relationship as Protective Factors for Chinese Adolescent Adjustment During COVID-19 This study examined the effects of perceived online learning difficulties and cyberbullying on academic engagement and mental health, and if parenting styles and student–teacher relationship moderated these relations among 733 middle school students (54.3% boys) and their parents (Mage= 44.76 years,SD = 4.13 years, 28.1 % fathers and 71.9% mothers) from Beijing, China.

CONCLUSION

Findings of the present study revealed that, the perception of parents had a moderately favourable attitude towards online teaching among school going students. The education should be seen as collaborative community exertion among teachers, parents, guardian and government to expand the viability of education and learning techniques that have been antagonistically influenced and guarantee the students not fall behind, the result of this study may be utilized as a baseline for planning awareness campaigns in the future.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

All the authors actively participated in the work of study.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Authors have declared that no conflict of interest.

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